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ISSUES OF IMPLEMENTING CIRCULAR ECONOMY PRINCIPLES IN RECYCLING INDUSTRIAL COMPLEXES

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Abstract: This study examines the integration of circular economy principles into Uzbekistan's processing industry. It explores contemporary scientific theories and international best practices in this field.

Key words: circular economy, principles, resource efficiency, green economy, business models, waste recycling, eco-technoparks, reuse, recycling, green technologies.

INTRODUCTION

The World Bank's 2024 analytical report, *"Circular Economy: Opportunities for Central Asia,"* explores the potential of the circular economy concept in the region, presents key findings relevant to Central Asian countries, and proposes solutions to common challenges in natural resource and waste management. The report highlights the need for further scientific research and a deeper study of international experiences.

The report defines the primary goal of the circular economy as minimizing the environmental impact of products and materials by recycling waste, conserving resources, and maximizing their lifespan. Additionally, it emphasizes the importance of developing sector-specific action strategies to guide future practical measures for achieving long-term goals in transitioning to a circular economy. These strategies will not only facilitate the identification and implementation of effective policy mechanisms but also stimulate private sector development. The report underscores that, with the right conditions in place, an accelerated transition to a circular economy is achievable.

The Republic of Uzbekistan, one of the first Central Asian countries to embrace the circular economy, is making significant strides toward sustainable development. On October 21, 2024, during a presentation on waste processing, electricity generation, and product manufacturing at the Central Asian University for Environmental and Climate Change Studies, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev set a national target for circular economy development. He stressed the critical importance of factories in this sector, stating: «These are not just factories; they are among the key factors determining our nation's future. The suitability of our land and water, public health, air quality, and energy stability all depend on this sector. If waste is collected properly and recycled efficiently, the ecological balance will improve, nature will be cleaner, and society will evolve.»

This statement underscores the urgency of advancing the waste processing industry in Uzbekistan. The sector is undergoing systematic improvements in the country. Notably, by a presidential decree dated September 26, 2024, the Agency for Waste Management and Circular Economy Development was established. This agency is responsible for implementing modern methods of waste collection, sorting, neutralization, recycling, incineration, utilization, and disposal.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the context of globalization and increasing resource scarcity, scientists worldwide are conducting extensive research and experiments to advance the circular economy and support the green economy.

Foreign scholar K. Warren, in his scientific vision, stated: «The circular economy is an alternative to the traditional economy, where resources are used for as long as possible, their maximum value is extracted during use, and products and materials are recovered and reused at the end of their lifecycle.» [6]

Economist J. Kirchherr, in his research, defined the circular economy as: «A system based on business models that replace the concept of 'end of life.' It operates on multiple levels: micro-level (products, companies, consumers), meso-level (eco-industrial parks), and macro-level (cities, regions, countries). By incorporating recycling and material recovery into production, distribution, and consumption processes, it ensures environmental sustainability, economic prosperity, and social justice for both present and future generations.» [7]

American scientist H. Wilts emphasized: «The fundamental idea behind developing a circular economy is to preserve the value of products as much as possible when they reach the end of their lifecycle.» [8]

Russian scholar A.V. Shishmaryova argued that: «The circular economy not only helps reduce the environmental impact of waste but also plays a crucial role in fostering technological, organizational, and social innovations.» [9]

Uzbek researcher M.N. Khudoyberdiyev shared his perspective, stating: «To fully establish an effective waste management infrastructure, it is essential to instill in society the idea that waste is a strategic resource with real economic benefits. This, in turn, will contribute to improving waste recycling and utilization in our country.» [10]

When determining the key directions for circular economy development, priorities vary depending on a country's development level. For developed nations, the focus is on structural changes in production and consumption, competitiveness, and job creation. In contrast, for developing countries, emphasis is placed on sustainable development and poverty reduction.

The table below highlights several leading countries that have initiated circular economy models in their economies.

Table 1. Advanced circular economy business models and leading countries that have implemented them.¹

Leading countries	Circular economy enterprises, organizations, programs and various initiatives
Japan	Euglena, Denso, Toyota Production Systems
Finland	TEKES, SITRA, North Europea Bio Tech Oy, Ponsse /sr-Harvesting, Swappie, Taitonetti, 3 Steplit
Netherlands	Netherlands as a Circular Hotspot, Madaster, DSM-Niaga, Royal DSM, Phillips, Circular Lighting, BMA Ergonomics, Koppert, Bundles, VDL Group, DAF Reblend
Great Britain	Unilever, Circularity Capital, Advanced Sustainable Developments, Waste and Resources Action Program, Earth Angel Inverters
USA	Ford, Heinz, Novellis, Ford Motor Company, POET-DSM Advanced Biofuels, Apple Renew, Ecovative, BalboGroup, Caterpillar Inc., Xerox
France	Renault Environmental, Roll-GOM, LeRelais, Baudalet, OuatecoBata, Sailbags 727, Alstom & HealthHub, Michelin
Denmark	Novo Nordisk, Novozymes, DONGEnergy, Statoil

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research process utilized scientific and theoretical methods such as deduction, classification, generalization, and comparison. Regulatory and legal documents necessary for scientific research were analyzed using statistical data collection and typological analysis methods.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

According to our research and analysis, the transition to a circular economy offers three undeniable advantages: reducing the negative impact on the environment by minimizing resource consumption in production, lowering production costs by decreasing the use of primary resources (raw materials), and facilitating the emergence of new markets and job creation, thereby contributing to overall economic well-being.

Countries, depending on their domestic economic policies, can implement the following business models either separately or in combination: the circular value chain model, where limited resources are entirely replaced by renewable sources, such as internal combustion engines operating on bioethanol and biodiesel derived from plant biomass instead of petroleum-based fuels; the product life cycle extension model, which involves remanufacturing, refurbishing, or reselling products to maintain their economic value for as long as possible,

¹ Prepared by the author based on Internet information.

while also shifting from selling physical goods to offering them as services; the sharing economy model, which is based on the shared use of underutilized goods or assets, with examples including shared transportation platforms like BlaBlaCar and accommodation services such as Airbnb; the product-as-a-service model, where customers use products by paying a recurring fee instead of purchasing them outright, as seen in companies offering lighting as a service while retaining ownership of the equipment, meaning customers do not pay for installation or maintenance, which are covered in the service contract; and the recycling and recovery model, which leverages innovative technologies for the recovery and reuse of resources, such as closed-loop recycling systems and the conversion of waste into new resources.

Given the above, waste recycling and reuse are fundamental elements of a circular economy. In this context, eco-technoparks play a crucial role in establishing key value chains. Eco-technological parks are specialized complexes equipped with scientific research facilities, green economy production units, modern laboratories, and technological infrastructure, focusing on the continuous processing of waste and the production of industrial products derived from recycled materials. A sustainable waste management system is largely based on the “Three R” principles: Reduce, Reuse, and Recycle, emphasizing reusing and recycling materials while limiting consumption to minimize waste generation. Currently, numerous circular economy models exist, many of which share common characteristics. However, the Ellen MacArthur Foundation’s circular economy model stands out due to its comprehensiveness and simplicity (Figure 1).

Figure 1. “Ellen MacArthur Fund” circular economy model. [11]

In our opinion, the transition to a circular economy model will reduce unnecessary consumption costs, promote the more efficient use of available resources, and mitigate ecological damage to the environment.

In Uzbekistan, too, the development of a circular economy is one of the priority areas of ongoing reforms at the state level. This is reflected in the development and implementation of targeted administrative and legal documents, the integration of green development principles into state programs, the introduction of measures to combat climate change and greenhouse gas emissions, the acceleration of renewable energy adoption, and the expansion of the waste processing industry.

As a result of the measures implemented to date, more than 20 official documents have been adopted in recent years, outlining over 154 initiatives aimed at the green transformation of the economy. In particular, these include the “Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the Transition to a Green Economy for 2019–2030”² [4], the Presidential Decree “On Measures to Increase the Effectiveness of Reforms Aimed at the

2 <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-4539502>

Transition to a Green Economy by 2030”³ [5], the Presidential Decree “On Accelerated Measures to Increase the Energy Efficiency of Economic and Social Sectors, the Introduction of Energy-Saving Technologies, and the Development of Renewable Energy Sources”, and the “Strategy for the Implementation of Work Related to Solid Household Waste for 2019–2028”⁴ [2].

The green technologies and energy sectors are considered the main drivers of the economy. Annually, an average of 14 million tons of waste are generated in Uzbekistan. However, only 4–5% of this waste is recycled. More than 7 million tons of greenhouse gases are released into the atmosphere from landfills, and 43,000 tons of toxic leachates seep into the ground [2].

In Uzbekistan, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 362-II⁵ “Law On Waste”, dated April 5, 2002, was adopted to prevent the harmful effects of waste on public health and the environment, reduce waste generation, and ensure its rational use in economic activities [1]. Article 2 of this law defines waste as “residues of raw materials, materials, semi-finished products, and other items or products formed during the production or consumption process, as well as goods (products) that have lost their consumer properties.”

Therefore, recycling waste not only reduces its environmental impact but also offers significant benefits as a renewable resource. Currently, solid waste collection and transportation services are primarily available in large cities of Uzbekistan. There are 296 landfills in the country designated for waste burial and disposal, including: 221 solid waste landfills, 16 industrial waste landfills, 4 construction waste landfills, 21 sludge collectors, 15 waste collection sites, 19 special landfills, 23 hazardous waste disposal sites.

Additionally, a system exists for the collection and transportation of mixed solid waste. The Strategy for the Implementation of Work Related to Solid Waste in the Republic of Uzbekistan for the Period 2019-2028 cites the following main problems related to solid waste:

- Insufficient provision of solid waste collection and disposal services in rural settlements;
- The infrastructure in the field of solid waste management is in an unsatisfactory state;
- Problems remain, such as the failure of existing solid waste landfills to meet sanitary requirements and environmental standards.

The volume of solid waste increased from 6.1 million tons in 2010 to 7.0 million tons in 2017 (UNECE, 2020). The Strategy for the Implementation of Solid Waste Management projects the annual volume of solid waste generation to be around 14-14.5 million tons. Taking into account the worst-case scenario, it is estimated that this figure could reach 16-16.7 million tons by 2028 [14].

The strategy sets many target indicators, such as increasing the coverage of the population with waste collection and disposal services to 100% and raising the level of solid waste recycling to 60% by 2028. Additionally, the newly developed Concept for Environmental Protection includes an increase in the volume of solid waste recycling to 65% as a target indicator.

The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the Development of Public-Private Partnerships in the Field of Solid Waste Management sets the goal of increasing the coverage of the population with solid waste collection and disposal services to 90% by the end of 2020 and 100% by the end of 2021, raising the volume of solid waste recycling to 21.8% by the end of 2020 and 36.5% by the end of 2021, and increasing the share of the private sector in the organization of solid waste collection and disposal services to 50% by the end of 2022. However, these tasks have not yet been fully implemented.

Climate change mitigation projects help reduce greenhouse gas emissions from waste, but they do not eliminate the growing volume of waste generated from production and consumption, which remains the main cause of increasing emissions. This issue is further exacerbated by the lack of regulatory provisions, standards, control mechanisms, information, and incentive measures for the reuse and recycling of materials.

The Strategy for the Implementation of Work on Solid Municipal Waste for 2019-2028 aims to create a new integrated waste management system, mainly due to the lack of an institutional and legal framework.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

To further advance the implementation of circular economy principles in processing industry complexes, it is essential to address several organizational and legal challenges. Firstly, existing standards for effective waste management are insufficient, and responsibilities for developing and operating a more integrated system are not clearly defined. Secondly, there is a lack of well-developed regulations ensuring sustainable financing for both infrastructure development and its continued operation. Thirdly, a comprehensive plan has not been established to create eco-industrial zones and eco-technological parks across various regions of the country and to fully integrate circular economy principles within them.

3 <https://lex.uz/docs/6303230>

4 <https://lex.uz/docs/4291729>

5 <https://lex.uz/en/docs/6817352>

Addressing these challenges will lay the foundation for the future growth of the industry and ensure long-term environmental sustainability. Based on the above considerations, it can be concluded that the widespread implementation of circular economy principles in processing industry complexes will contribute to stabilizing the ecological situation, increasing energy efficiency, significantly reducing harmful gas emissions, improving sanitary conditions, and decreasing the incidence of environmentally related diseases among the population. Furthermore, waste processing will be enhanced, and the production of alternative energy, raw materials, and organic fertilizers will be accelerated. Modern eco-industrial zones and eco-technological parks will be established on the sites of existing landfills, creating opportunities for the accelerated adoption of an economic model based on zero-waste technology, ensuring sustainable resource utilization from raw materials to finished products.

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